

MATHEMATICAL METHOD FOR RECORDING AND RESTORING DIGITAL HOLOGRAPHIC IMAGES

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Introduction

There is no area of human activity where one can do without quantitative assessments obtained through measurements. The development of information and measurement systems takes industrial monitoring to a new level, making it more precise, accessible, faster, and cheaper.

Depending on the nature of the effect on an object, destructive and non-destructive testing methods are distinguished.

Among the many non-destructive testing methods, optical methods stand out [1]. These methods are based on the properties of wave fields and allow measurements with an accuracy of up to hundredths and thousandths of a wavelength used for monitoring.

With the advent of holography, it became possible to conduct interferometric measurements not only of transparent and mirror-like objects (i.e., objects with optically clean surfaces) but also of diffusely reflecting objects. Holography is a method of recording an arbitrary wave front that allows capturing both the amplitude and phase of oscillation, and then reproducing them at any convenient time. Since complete information about the shape of an object is contained in the optical field scattered by the illuminated object, the holographic process allows for registering this shape in an unchanged form. The shape preserved in this way can be reproduced at any time and used as a template. Most methods of optical non-destructive testing that utilize holography are based on this principle. Methods that compare two states of an object using holography are referred to as holographic interferometry.

Holographic interferometry has expanded the functional capabilities of optical interferometry by enabling measurements of diffusely reflecting objects. The optical properties of surfaces and the complexity of object shapes are no longer limiting factors, making holographic interferometry suitable for investigating industrial parts and structures in factory conditions.

The development of computer technologies, along with the complexity of processing classical holograms, has created a need to work with digital holograms based on digital technologies.

The process of decoding digital holograms is performed using computer technology, which allows, firstly, to obtain and store results in a more user-friendly format, and, secondly, to utilize previously inaccessible processing and analysis methods. This opens new perspectives for developing holographic measurement systems. By tracing the trends in the development of coherent optical measurement, control, and diagnostic systems in the near future, it can be concluded that they consist of 10% optics, 10% mechanics, 20% electronics, and 60% algorithmic and mathematical support. Therefore, developing new algorithmic approaches, decoding methods, and mathematical methods for processing and obtaining holographic images is of great importance.

Main Part

To mathematically describe the interaction of wave fields in holographic interferometry, we will use the complex amplitude method [2]. If a plane electromagnetic wave is described by the equation:

$$E(r, t) = E_0 e^{-i[\omega t - kr + \varphi_0]} \quad (1)$$

then the complex amplitude does not include the time component ωt and the initial phase φ_0 , i.e.,

$$E(r, t) = E_0 e^{ikr} \quad (2)$$

Here, E_0 is the amplitude of the electric field intensity vector in the electromagnetic wave, which exactly corresponds to the amplitude in the equation.

In holographic interferometry, two restored wave fields E_{01} and E_{02} interact, corresponding to two states of the object.

$$E_p = E_{01} + E_{02} \quad (3)$$

At this point, the intensity of the restored image is described by the expression

$$I_p = E_p E_p^* = E_{01} E_{01}^* + E_{02} E_{02}^* + (E_{01} E_{02}^* + E_{01}^* E_{02}) = \quad (4)$$

$$I_{01} + I_{02} + (E_{01} E_{02}^* + E_{01}^* E_{02}) = 2[I_0 + \sin(Kz)] = 4I_0 \cos^2\left(\frac{zL}{2}\right),$$

where $K = k_{i1} - k_{o1} = k_{i2} - k_{o2}$ is the holographic sensitivity vector, and z is the displacement vector of the object point.

The process of restoring digital holograms occurs numerically using the Fresnel-Kirchhoff diffraction integral:

$$I(x_2, y_2, z) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} I_H(x_1, y_1) \cdot \frac{\exp(iKz)}{i\lambda z} \cdot \exp\left\{\frac{iK}{2z} [(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2]\right\} dx_1 \cdot dy_1 \quad (5)$$

where - the complex amplitude of the restored field in the plane at a distance z from the hologram plane, - the intensity distribution recorded by the CCD camera, - the wavelength, and - the wave number.

In the restored holographic images of particles, there are noise patterns in the form of bands that repeat the shapes of the objects. This noise complicates the extraction of object contours and subsequent identification. They are caused by the following reasons: during the restoration process in the restoration plane, the overlap of three waves occurs: the wave corresponding to the real image located in this plane, the wave propagating from the imaginary image located at a distance of $2z$ from the real one, and the wave passing through the hologram

without changing its direction. The interference of the first two waves in the restored image leads to the aforementioned bands

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